

A Panorama of Spectacular Molecular and Cellular Principles of Metastasis

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ABSTRACT

The characteristic of cancer that causes the most deaths from the disease is metastasis. About 90% of all cancer-related deaths are caused by metastases, making them the main cause of cancer-related morbidity and mortality. One in three people will receive a cancer diagnosis at some point in their lives, making it the second leading cause of death in developed countries. On the surface, the disease appears to be spreading throughout developed nations based on incidence data from the last century or so. However, more people are living to an age where they are more susceptible to cancer, which is primarily a disease of later life, as a result of advancements in medical and public health science. Understanding the molecular mechanisms underlying the metastatic process is necessary to identify treatment windows that are open for effective interventions. This review covers recent developments in the field of metastasis as well as the latest research that has influenced this aspect of cancer. Lastly, new treatments are being developed as we gain more knowledge about the biology of cancer. With genomes and biopharmaceuticals playing a big part, this has been one of the most productive areas of drug research in recent years, and the innovation seems to be continuing.

Keywords: Cancer metastasis, Molecular mechanisms of metastasis, Cancer-related mortality, Biopharmaceutical innovations in oncology, Age-related cancer incidence.

INTRODUCTION

The word “Metastasis” in Greek means “displacement” and the word “stasis” means “placement”. Cancer metastasis is the term used to describe the movement of tumor cells from a primary tumor cell to another site through lymphatic and blood vessels. The term “metastasis” describes the development of secondary tumors in a body part that is distant from the original primary cancer. The final and most deadly stage of cancer is metastasis, which is the growth of cancer cells in organs other than the one in which they first appeared. Rather than primary tumors, the majority of cancer patients pass away as a result of their metastatic disease. The term “metastasis” refers to a sequence of biological processes whereby cells from a primary tumor gradually develop the ability to penetrate deeper

tissues through the mucosa; spread via the blood, lymphatics, or direct infiltration of nearby structures; seed distant organs; and ultimately resume proliferation at distant sites to colonize these organs.¹ Metastasis has a major effect on the prognosis of cancer patients. Little is known about metastasis, despite the fact that it is the main reason why cancer treatments fail and people die. Research on melanoma in animal models shows that less than 0.1% of tumor cells spread, despite the fact that cancer patients release a large number of cancer cells into the bloodstream each day. Several theories have been proposed to explain the mechanism of metastasis. The “organ selection concept” growth factors are required for a metastasis to successfully occur at the metastatic site. As per the “adhesion theory” the migratory cancer cells establish a premetastatic microenvironment by being anchored by tissue-

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specific adhesion molecules that are expressed on the endothelial cells of the destination organs. Cancer cells expression of chemokine receptors is explained by the “chemo-attraction theory”. Paget first proposed the idea of seed for metastatic tumor cells and soil for the secondary site in 1889. According to this theory, the organs distribution is determined by the original tumor location and histology.

For metastasis to take place, cancer cells must escape their original location, move through the bloodstream, endure blood vessel pressure, adjust to new biological conditions in a secondary location, and avoid deadly immune cell combat. One of the traits of cancer, according to Hanahan and Weinberg, is activating invasion and metastasis. Actually, the invasion of nearby tissue and the seeding of distant locations to produce metastases remain two of the basic features of cancer malignancy. The estimated number of cancer cases in India is 13.9 lakh, and by 2025, that number may increase to 15.7 lakh, as metastasis is the primary cause of death for over 90% of cancer patients. According to the Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR), there will be a 12% rise in cancer cases in India over the course of the next five years. Men are more likely than women to get cancer overall (52.4%) compared to 47.4%. This article aims to provide a general overview of the metastatic process and intervention targets, with a focus on cancer cell adhesion, migration, invasion, and dissociation. This review is meant to serve as a starting point for anyone interested in cancer metastasis and intervention²

1. PATHOGENESIS

Developmental Stages

- 1) Cell mitigation & Membrane invasion in basement membrane.
- 2) Disruption of the environment's lymphatic or vascular systems.
- 3) Staying alive in the blood.
- 4) Subsequent vascular system-mediated tissue extravasation.

1.1 INVASION AND DISSEMINATION

Chromosome instability is the first trigger. Prior to the first phases of the invasive metastatic cascade, cancer cells begin to spread. The process by which a

cancerous cell or tumor spreads from its original location and makes its way to another organ is known as dissemination. The cascade results from chromosomal instability brought on by chromosome segregation failures that occur repeatedly during mitosis. These failures cause micronuclei to rupture and genomic DNA to be secreted into the cytosol, which in turn triggers downstream nuclear factor κ -light-chain-enhancer of activated B (NF- κ B) signaling and cycles of GMP-AMP synthase–stimulator of interferon (IFN) genes, and additional cytosolic DNA-sensing pathways. The process by which altered epithelial cells gain the ability to invade, endure stress, and multiply is termed as EMT. Because of their strong attachment to the extracellular matrix (ECM) and to one another, epithelial cells are immobile. EMT confers epithelial–mesenchymal plasticity, which is critical for the growth and spread of cancer, and controls the reversible biochemical alterations that enable a particular epithelial cell to take on a mesenchymal phenotype. Disseminated tumor cells can be eliminated by high oxidative stress, lack of supportive growth factors or nutrients and active hostile immune defense in form of tissue-specific migration and invasion.³

1.2 INTRAVASATION

Intravasation is the first mechanism by which cancer cells break through the vessel wall and enter the bloodstream. Cancer cells can spread to organs either actively or passively through the lumen of the vasculature, a process known as intravasation. The tumor type, the microenvironment, and the circulatory system all have a consequence. Using live-cell fluorescence microscopy and a tissue-engineered tumor-micro-vessel platform, a mitosis-mediated method was described in which tumor cells positioned along the vessel periphery damage the vessel endothelium by cell division and detach into circulation. A three-dimensional microfluidic model revealed that the endothelium functions as a barrier to tumor cells and is regulated by components found in the tumor's microenvironment². Additionally, the tissue's architectural constraints place some mechanical strain on the invasive tumor cells during intravasation. Genetic rearrangement follows, raising the possibility of metastatic spread. Integrins are crucial cellular adhesion receptors that are involved in

almost all phases of the development of cancer, from simple tumor growth to metastasis. Integrin expression is frequently changed in malignancies, and they play a role in oncogenic growth factor receptor (GFR) signaling as well as GFR-dependent cancer cell motility and invasion. By promoting anchorage-independent survival of tumor cells in circulation (CTCs), integrins also contribute to the colonization of metastatic locations. E-cadherin has to exist for the split, multiplication, and implanting of metastatic cells in metastatic sites. By doing this, reactive oxygen-induced apoptosis is avoided and metastatic cell survival is increased⁴.

1.3 CIRCULATION

Cancer can spread to distant sites by following pathways:

- 1) Lymphatic spread
- 2) Hematogenous spread
- 3) Disperse throughout the body's natural passageways and cavities.

A cell that has shed from a primary tumor into the lymphatics or vasculature and is transported throughout the body by the blood circulation is known as a circulating tumor cell (CTC). Interactions between CTCs and the microenvironmental elements of circulation impact their survival and ability to spread to far-off areas. While some CTCs travel in clusters, the bulk circulate as solitary cells. Circulating clusters, on the opposite hand, are much more probable to spread. In addition to the invasive cancer cells, clusters also contain stromal cells and

immune elements from the original milieu, which support the cluster's survival and heterogeneity. Neutrophils increase the likelihood of CTC survival by reducing leukocyte activation and assisting in cluster formation.

1.4 COLONIZATION

Circulating cells that extravasate at the target site face hostile conditions that make survival difficult. Cancer cells invade and migrate through the stroma due to cytoskeletal changes inside the cells, as well as the activity of sticky interactions, secreted extracellular matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs), and cathepsins. A broad range of factors are released by bone marrow-derived cells and tumors. It indicates the existence of the PMN, a site of tumor cell infiltration and proliferation. Apart from chemicals originating from tumors, exosomes also have a significant role. Bone marrow progenitor cells learn to proliferate with the aid of exosomes. On the other hand, interactions between host cells and cancer cells are essential for successful colonization. The liver is particularly susceptible to metastatic colonization because hepatocytes control the accumulation of myeloid cells and fibrosis in the organ. In mice models of pancreatic cancer, hepatocytes enhance the formation of serum amyloid A1 and A2 and activate IL-6-mediated STAT3 signaling (SAA). PMN development is inhibited and the spread of liver metastases are decreased when IL-6-STAT3-SAA signaling is inhibited. The construction of a vascular network is vital for appropriate metastatic colonization. Neural signaling pathways can also be used by colonizing cancer cells to proliferate and adapt⁵.

Figure No. 1: Overview of the Metastatic Cascade

1.5 DORMANCY IN METASTATIC CLUSTERS

Dormancy occurs when the rate of cellular division within a metastatic cancer cluster is equal to the rate of apoptosis. The tumor cluster does not progress to the stage of micrometastasis as a result. This balance is achieved through restricted angiogenesis, suppressed gene signaling, and/or an active immunological milieu. One tumor suppressor gene that can be exploited to trigger suppressive gene signaling is Differentially expressed in Chondrocytes 2 (DEC2). Through the activation of p27 and the inhibition of cyclin-dependent kinase 4, TGF β -induced DEC2 production causes the cell to enter a latent state. When thrombospondin-1 is activated or chaperones such as heat shock 27 kDa protein are inhibited, blood vessel formation is stopped, pushing metastatic clusters into a latent state. Additionally, the immune system aids in stopping the spread of cancer. To get rid of metastatic cells, T cells, NK cells, and macrophages employ cytotoxicity. Relapse after immunotherapy may be caused by latent tumor cells expressing weak antigens to evade the immune system.

2. METASTATIC CELL GENETIC PROFILE

The various cell types that make up metastatic cancer have distinct genetic and phenotypic traits that influence medication resistance, metastasis, and progression in different ways. It has been discovered that an extensive number of genes are linked to invasive potential, indicating that the initial tumor cells carry a genetic signature that spreads to additional tumor cells. The genetic basis of cancer has been identified as oncogenes, which are altered versions of normal cellular genes involved in growth control. Although oncogenic transformation is a precursor to tumor formation, it is not invariably linked to the metastatic phenotype. In certain cell lines, certain oncogenes can cause metastatic characteristics, but not in others. There are currently three known human isoforms: NRAS, HRAS, and KRAS. However, in the presence of certain homozygous allelic manifestations, certain mutations may continue to promote invasion and metastasis. Integrative clinical genomics (ICG) revealed that the most commonly somatically altered genes in metastasis were tumor protein p53 (TP53), cyclic

independent kinase inhibitor 2A (CDKN2A), phosphatase and tensin homolog (PTEN), retinoblastoma, and phosphatidylinositol-4,5-bisphosphate 3-kinase catalytic subunit alpha (PIK3CA). According to markers that indicate metastatic progression, advanced malignancies arise from a range of cell types, which significantly influences the final genetic and epigenetic alterations that promote metastatic progression.

Cells with metastatic small cell lung cancer (SCLC) express distinct genes. This may help to explain why certain cancer cells react well to treatment while others don't. Therefore, understanding intertumoral heterogeneity in various cancers can help uncover mechanisms of metastatic progression and the ways in which the type of cell that originated the tumor affects its creation. The chemoresistance and metastasis-initiating characteristics of colorectal cancer are attributed to cells that express the L1 cell adhesion molecule (L1CAM). By taking advantage of intestinal cells' capacity for regeneration, L1CAM encourages metastasis. Moreover, the presence of lymphatic capillaries and the cytotoxic immune signature are important factors in the development of distant metastases, irrespective of the type of cancer⁶⁻⁷.

2.1 METABOLIC PROFILE OF METASTATIC CELL:

Tumor hypoxia is correlated with a poor prognosis in clinical settings. Through its regulation of angiogenesis, EMT, invasion, metastasis, and energy metabolism, hypoxia inducible factor (HIF) enables cancer cells to adjust to their biological environment. Expression of HIF-1 α and HIF-2 α is associated with patient mortality. Treatment resistance and tumor aggressiveness are typically linked to these and other hypoxia-related factors. Furthermore, tumors with larger hypoxic and anoxic zones are more likely to metastasize. Variations in the metastatic potential of cancer cells are influenced by variations in their metabolic potential. MCT1, or monocarboxylate transporter 1, aids in the defense against oxidative stress in metastatic cancer cells. One of the main energy sources for metastasizing cells is lactate, which is circulated by MCT1. MCT1 levels are therefore higher in highly metastatic cells, while MCT1 inhibition reduces lactate uptake by metastatic

cells, hence reducing their capacity to spread. Metastatic behavior may be encouraged by changes in the ratios of ATP/ADP and ATP/AMP. Through cellular adhesion and compression, ECM remodeling in pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma affects these ratios. Such changes, according to metabolomics, boost the production of phosphocreatine, which is involved in the invasion, migration, chemotaxis, and liver metastasis of cancer cells.

2.2 EPITHELIAL-MESENCHYMAL TRANSITION IN METASTASIS

A developmental mechanism known as the epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT) gives stationary epithelial cells the capacity to invade and move as individual cells. In addition to being linked to an increase in cell mobility, EMT is also characterized as a characteristic that preserves stem cell

characteristics, inhibits apoptosis and senescence, suppresses the immune system and gains resistance to radiation and chemotherapy. In order to acquire genetic changes that allow for the partial loss of epithelial characteristics and the partial acquisition of a mesenchymal phenotype, tumor cells reactivate EMT. EMT may arise because to either group migration or single-cell dissemination. Immobile, epithelial cells are firmly attached to the surrounding extracellular matrix (ECM) and to one another. EMT gives epithelial cells epithelial-mesenchymal plasticity, which is essential for the spread and metastasis of cancer, and regulates the reversible biochemical changes that allow a particular epithelial cell to become a mesenchymal phenotype. Because asparagine encourages EMT, lowering asparagine levels with L-asparaginase therapy or dietary restriction slows the spread of metastases⁸.

Figure No. 2: Epithelial-Mesenchymal Transition

2.3 PRE-METASTATIC NICHE

A pre-metastatic niche (PMN) is formed in the bone when multiple distal niche cells interact with the initially present tumor cells. These interactions promote molecular and cellular changes in distant organs, facilitating metastatic seeding before collective and large metastases are clinically detectable. The PMN lays down the foundation for organ tropism. Fibroblasts, for instance, have a vital role in establishing the requirements necessary for metastatic colonization. Periostin expression has a strong effect on the growth of early disseminated cancer stem cells at secondary sites, demonstrating the role of

fibroblasts in establishing a metastatic niche and the signals from stromal niches.

likewise, the tumor associated stroma, comprised of fibroblasts, vigorously encourages tumor growth and organizes distal seeding, including bone colonization, by promoting neo-angiogenesis and the growth and invasion of cancer cells. The development of PMN in the lungs and the planning of lung and brain metastases from various cancer types are significantly affected by secreted extracellular vesicles (sEVs). Within the numerous substances present in sEVs that have the potential to impact cellular functions are metabolites, lipids, enzymes, and nucleic acids.⁹⁻¹⁰

2.4 METASTASIS NICHE

In cancer, the microenvironment builds the proliferation of metastases, or new tumors in distant organs. The habitat at the distant target organ that is triggered by things from the original site is known as the pre-metastasis niche. The term "pre-metastatic niche" implies to an environment in which cancer cells grow. An active microenvironment developed through interactions between cancer cells and the host stroma is known as a metastatic niche. This niche effectively promotes the development of metastases and the growing incidence of cancer. The primary tumor preferentially primes for the existence of a premetastatic niche (PMN) even before metastases manifest. PMN-causing cytokines and enzymes may be screened by the primary tumor through the release of exosomes and tumor cell secretion factor. Modifications to host cells (fibroblasts), and the recruitment of non-resident cells (hematopoietic progenitor cells).¹¹⁻¹²

2.5 METASTATIC ORGANOTROPISM

The non-random scattering of metastases between distant organs can be referred to as "organotropism". Paget first introduced organotropism with respect to the "seed and soil" theory. As stated by Stephan Paget, the expansion of metastases relies on the availability of favorable ME ("soil") and the fundamental characteristics of cancer cells ("seed"). By outlining the genetic basis for cancer colonization in distant organs, researchers studying breast cancer have provided verification in to back up this theory. Additionally, the extravasation and colonization of cancer cells at certain locations is determined by the host microenvironment and the adaptive process that invasive cancer cells go through. It is feasible for breast cancer to spread to the liver, brain, lung, and bone.

Figure No. 3: Metastatic Organotropism

Metastatic seeds are resistant to treatment and can migrate between the osteogenic niche and cancer cells, as evidenced by the discovery of a crosstalk mechanism in the progression of bone metastasis that stimulates calcium flux, frequently after a lengthy latency. Another example is patients with postpartum breast cancer, who are at a higher risk of liver

metastases. The identification of weaning-induced liver involution, which produces a metastatic milieu, is one explanation for the poor prognosis of women with postpartum breast cancer. Among the factors governing organotropism are the circulation pattern, tumor intrinsic factors, organ-specific niches, and the

interaction between tumor cells and the host microenvironment¹³.

Table 1. Common sites where cancer spread¹³.

CANCER TYPE	MAIN SITE OF METASTASIS
Bladder	Bone, Liver, Lungs
Breast	Bone, Brain, Liver, Lungs
Colon	Liver, Lungs, Peritoneum
Kidney	Adrenal gland, Bone
Lung	Liver, Lungs
Ovary	Liver, Lung, Peritoneum
Uterus	Bone, Liver, Vagina
Melanoma	Bone, Brain, Liver, Lungs, Skin, Muscle
Pancreas	Liver, Lungs, Peritoneum
Prostate	Adrenal gland, Bone, Liver, Lung
Rectal	Liver, Lung, Peritoneum
Stomach	Liver, lung, peritoneum
Thyroid	Bone, Liver, lung

3. SIGNS AND SYMPTOMS¹⁴

Metastatic cancer symptoms are not always evident. The kind of symptoms you have and how often they happen will depend on the size and location of the metastatic tumors. Some common signs of metastatic cancer include the following:

- Pain and fractures may result from cancer that has spread throughout the body and to the bones.
- When brain cancer spreads, it can cause headaches, dizziness, or convulsions.
- Breathlessness in cases of advanced lung cancer.
- The patient may have abdominal swelling or jaundice if liver cancer has spread.
- Two common signs of lymph node metastases are fever and lymphadenopathy.
- Coughing, hemoptysis, and dyspnea are signs of lung metastases.
- Liver metastases are indicated by hepatomegaly (enlarged liver), nausea, and jaundice.
- People with bone metastases may experience back pain and fractures.

3.1 DIAGNOSTIC TEST FOR METASTASIS TUMORS

It is necessary to confirm a diagnosis that is suspected after a clinical examination and further testing. The

biopsy's histological analysis is the most dependable and conclusive technique that holds up over time. A tumor's size, location, and presence can be determined using a variety of test types. To provide a more precise diagnosis, they are frequently combined. The most popular tests are as follows:

1) Histological methods

- Paraffin-embedding technique
- Frozen section

2) Cytological methods

- Exfoliative cytology
- Fine needle aspiration cytology

3) Histochemistry and Cytochemistry

Other techniques included are,

- X-ray (mammography)
- Ultrasound (sonography)
- Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI)
- Bone scan (Bone scintigraphy)
- Computed tomography

- Fluorescent in-situ hybridization (FISH)
- Biopsy

Following the completion of the diagnostic test, the location, size, and extent of tumor spread are assessed in order to study the progression of cancer. The stage of the tumor is then identified as 0, I, II, III, and IV, and the appropriate treatment is administered¹⁵⁻¹⁶.

3.2 THERAPEUTIC STRATEGIES TO TARGET PATHWAYS OF METASTASIS

The dearth of treatment trials that are specifically focused on metastases and our limited understanding of the molecular mechanisms underlying the metastatic process are two major challenges. The genetic and phenotypic distinctions between parental and metastatic/circulating cancer cells must be taken into account when creating targeted treatments for metastatic cancer cells. The diagnosis of metastatic cancer is still linked to the mortality prognosis. Despite preclinical evidence of metastasis prevention, poor trial design and therapeutic approaches have impeded drug development. Improvements in immunotherapy have enhanced patient outcomes and survival in cases of metastatic melanoma.

Additionally, the development of new androgen receptor inhibitors has improved the prognosis for patients with metastatic prostate cancer. Long-term follow-ups haven't shown any consistent survival benefits for patients with metastatic breast cancer. Strategies that target pathways in the metastatic cascade have been studied and developed. It is possible to stop cancer cells from seeding by taking advantage of protease release, EMT, intravasation, intertumoral interactions, and intercellular crosstalk via ECM adhesion molecules. However, cancer cells may have already implanted themselves in the circulatory system or colonized a distant location by the time metastatic discovery occurs. Therefore, focusing on metastatic colonization appears to be the most practical therapeutic approach because it most closely resembles the clinical scenario. Because of their potential for diagnosis and prognosis, exosomes are helpful for liquid biopsies in addition to CTCs. The brain continues to be a unique location for metastases because the blood-brain barrier (BBB) provides invasive cells with a safe haven. The BBB allows cancerous cells to pass through while blocking the passage of therapeutic drugs. This calls for the creation of new medications that can cross the blood-brain barrier and the study of existing therapies that can do so in brain metastasis models.

Figure No. 4: Metastasis suppressor

3.3 ANTICANCER DRUGS

TYPE	GROUP	EXAMPLE	MAIN MECHANISM
Alkylating and related agents	Nitrogen mustard Nitrosoureas Platinum compounds	Cyclophosphamide ,chlorambucil Lomustine , Carmustine Carboplatin , Cisplatin	Intrastrand cross-linking DNA
Antimetabolites	Folate antagonist Pyrimidine pathway Purine pathway	Methotrexate,raltitrexed Flurouracil , capecitabine Cladibrine , Mercaptopurine	Blocking the synthesis of DNA/RNA
Cytotoxic antibiotics	Anthracyclines Others	Doxorubicin ,Epirubicin Mitomycin , Dactinomycin	Multiple effect on DNA synthesis and topoisomerase action
Plant derivatives	Taxanes Vinca alkaloids Camptothecins Other	Paclitaxel , docetaxel Vinblastine , vincristine , vindesine Irinotecan , topotecan Etoposide	Microtubule assembly; prevents spindle formation. Inhibition of topoisomerase
Hormones/antagonist	Hormones /analouges Antagonist Aromatase inhibitor	Diethylstilbestrol,ethinyloestradiol Leuporelin , lanreotide Tamoxifen , toremifene , fulvestrant Anastrozole , letrozole	Act as physiological antagonists , antagonists or hormone synthesis inhibitors to disrupt hormone-dependent tumour growth
Protine kinase inhibitor	Tyrosine kinase inhibitors Pan kinase inhibitor	Dasatinib , erlotinib , imatinib Sorafenib	Inhibition of kinases involved in growth factor receptor transduction
Monoclonal antibodies	Anti-EGF, EGF-2 ANTI-CD20/CD52 Anti-VEGF-	Panitumumab, trastuzumab Rituximab, alemtuzumab Rituximab, alemtuzumab Bevacizumab	Blocks cell proliferation Inhibiton of lymphocyte proliferation Prevents angiogenesis

4. DEVELOPMENT IN THE FUTURE

4.1 Angiogenic Inhibitors

Anti-angiogenic medications are used to restrict the blood flow to tumor tissue in order to prevent tumor growth and spread. Despite being molecular and mechanical research on angiogenic inhibitors continues to concentrate on VEGF signaling pathway because of its dominance in the angiogenesis system,

despite studies showing that several regulators are involved in tumor angiogenesis. The two most common medications used in anti-angiogenic therapy are small molecule tyrosine kinase inhibitors and recombinant monoclonal antibodies. FDA approved angiogenic inhibitors for clinical use monoclonal antibodies that are anti-angiogenic. The source of monoclonal antibodies is synthetically generated hybridoma cells, which possess the benefits of reduced cross reactivity, great specificity, high

sensitivity and high purity. These immediate, distinct benefits in clinical treatment are relatively advantageous to patients in comparison to kinase inhibitors. Bevacizumab is the most representative antibody. The macromolecular recombinant human monoclonal antibody bevacizumab referred to as first formal angiogenic inhibitor, neutralizes all VEGF isoforms to prevent tumor angiogenesis by blocking the transduction of VEGF pathway¹⁷.

In phase III clinical study using IFL treatment (irinotecan, leucovorin and fluorouracil) the PFS rate of previously addition of bevacizumab resulted in rise

in median length of response of 3.3 months, an increase in the OS rate from 34.8%-44.8% and increase in median number of untreated metastatic CRC patients from 6.2 months to 10.6 months. Therefore, in 2004 the FDA approved bevacizumab for use in individuals with colorectal cancer. Bevacizumab has been licensed for use as monotherapy as a surgical adjuvant, or in combination with chemotherapy for a number of different tumors in addition to the original indication. Clinical trials are now being conducted to examine the drugs potential in antiangiogenic therapy^{18,19}.

Figure No. 5: Angiogenic Inhibitors

4.2 Matrix Metalloproteinases inhibitors (MMPs)

According to recent research, MMP-1 strongly correlates with the poor outcomes of malignancies and encourages the invasion and migration of cancer cells. Breast, Stomach, Bladder and oral malignancies have all been found to have elevated MMP-1 expression, which has been associated with a bad prognosis for these conditions. Research indicates that MMP-1 promotes the growth and invasion of breast cancer cells by cleaving the same arg-ser bond as thrombin. Protease activated receptor (PAR) activation ultimately results from this, aiding in invasion and growth of breast cancer cells. Furthermore, MMP-1 has been connected by wang et al. to promotion of malignant behavior in colorectal

cancer through the AKT signaling pathway and the epithelial mesenchymal transition (EMT)²⁰. According to different study, patients with esophageal squamous cell carcinoma who had higher expression levels of MMP-1 and vascular endothelial growth factor-C (VEGF-C) had a worse prognosis and an advanced tumor stage. Moreover, MMP-1 overexpression was connected to the invasiveness of primary nodular melanoma. These results suggest that medication alters MMP expression or activity may be employed to treat cancer²¹.

Combinatorial chemistry and structure-based design have been used to generate a number of synthetic chemical inhibitors. The first drugs created were broad spectrum inhibitors that worked against a

variety of MMPs. Because of their poor musculoskeletal effects, reduced in vivo efficacy, and restricted oral absorption advanced clinical trials involving them were therefore failed. The most common adverse effect musculoskeletal syndrome

(MSS), has an unclear cause. However, it was once believed that MMP-1 inhibition played a role. Consequently, there has been increased interest MMP inhibitors that spare MMP-1²².

Figure No 6: Matrix Metalloproteinases inhibitors

4.3 Cyclo-Oxygenase Inhibitors

Significant epidemiological and experimental evidence suggests that long-term usage of cyclo-oxygenase (COX) inhibitors protects against gastrointestinal tract cancer as well as cancer in other potential sites. Since the COX-2 isoform is overexpressed in about 85% of cancers, prostanoids from this source may activate signaling pathways that prevent cells from dying. In animal models, celecoxib, a COX-2 inhibitor, accelerates tumor regression and lowers the risk of gastrointestinal and breast cancer. As a colon tumor inhibitor, it is presently undergoing human testing. While others argue that the mechanism of action is unrelated to COX inhibition, COX-2 is currently considered a promising target for anticancer therapeutic research. The literature is daunting and frequently controversial²³.

4.4 Antisense Oligonucleotides

Genetic methods are the way of the future, according to several specialists. Single-stranded DNA sequences known as antisense oligonucleotides are complementary to certain mRNA coding areas and have the ability to reduce gene expression. The antiapoptotic factor is inhibited by the antisense drug Augmerosen. Bcl-2. In an early clinical experiment, it made malignant melanoma more sensitive to common anticancer medications²⁴⁻²⁵.

5. GENE THERAPY

Delivering genes (DNA, RNA, mRNA, siRNA, Antisense oligonucleotides, etc) to patients in order to fix damaged genes that cause disease is known as gene therapy. Gene therapy medicinal products (GTMP) are categorized as advanced therapeutic

medicinal goods by European medicine agency (EMA). Drugs used for are sophisticated technological goods that contain genes with therapeutic preventative or diagnostic effects. They are used to repair damaged tissue, restore deficient areas to keep body functioning properly and stop undesirable genes from being expressed²⁶.

Gene Therapy can be performed via different mechanisms:

- Replacing a mutated, disease-causing gene with healthy copy
- Inhibiting expression of mutated gene
- Silencing unwanted gene
- Replacing defective genes

Tumor cell growth is slowed via gene silence and inhibition, such as the use of nuclear phthalate or antisense RNA to suppress the production of certain oncogenes. Transducing cells with a gene capable of converting an inert prodrug into harmful agent is method used in suicide gene therapy. The term "gene directed enzyme prodrug therapy" describes suicide gene therapy techniques that employ drugs that have been deactivated. Gene replacement therapy uses a vector to introduce a healthy copy of a gene into cancer cells by identifying a specific gene mutation in those cells. Vectors which are delivery mechanisms for genetic material, can be either viral or non-viral. The goal of gene therapy is to use a secure, reliable and efficient carrier to deliver therapeutic genes to target cells.²⁷ Gene therapy When it comes to selective toxicity to cancer cells, gene therapy—which employs altered genes, antisense oligonucleotides, or siRNA—offers many benefits over conventional therapies. There are still numerous unresolved technical problems with delivering genes (such growth factor antisense DNA) into target cells. Clinical trials have been conducted, with some showing minor success, but progress has been disappointingly slow²⁸⁻²⁹.

CONCLUSION

The multi-step process of metastasis includes invasion and dissemination, intravasation, circulation, extravasation, and colonization. Metastasis involves

numerous chemicals and signaling pathways. Metastases can be easily identified using a range of diagnostic techniques thanks to reliable detection techniques. The prognosis determines the treatment plan for patients with advanced cancer, and metastasis is a critical predictor of survival. Metastasis is the primary cause of cancer-related mortality worldwide. The field of molecular pathology and new diagnostic methods have grown rapidly. According to recent genetic and molecular research, a successful metastasis requires the accumulation of mutations, the development of a pre-metastatic niche, and the acquisition of more invasive phenotypes. The last stage of cancer where stronger therapies are required is metastasis. However, developing effective treatments necessitates comprehending the basic principles that underpin the entire metastatic process. Consequently, studying metastatic evolution is crucial to creating more potent therapies. Clarifying mechanisms like EMT involved in both healthy and diseased physiological processes has led to significant advancements. It is believed that identifying specific and important genes that contribute to the spread of cancer and investigating the genetic pathways that underlie these genes are essential steps in developing drugs that can stop metastases. This study highlights recent scientific advancements that focus on innovative approaches to diagnosis and treatment, and it provides guidance on various indications and stages of cancer metastasis. It also focuses on the immunological environment of the primary site, The genetic makeup of metastatic cells and metastatic organotropism.

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